

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
ANTI-PHISHING IN ANDROID PHONE PROJECT REPORT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Phishing is a new word produced from 'fishing', it refers to the act that the attacker allure users to visit a faked Web site by sending them faked e-mails (or instant messages), and stealthily get victim's personal information such as user name, password, and national security ID, etc. This information then can be used for future target advertisements or even identity theft attacks (e.g., transfer money from victims' bank account). The frequently used attack method is to send e-mails to potential victims, which seemed to be sent by banks, online organizations, or ISPs. In these e-mails, they will make up some causes, e.g. the password of your credit card had been mis-entered for many times, or they are providing upgrading services, to allure you visit their Web site to conform or modify your account number and password through the hyperlink provided in the e-mail (Leon, 2008).

If you input the account number and password, the attackers then successfully collect the information at the server side, and is able to perform their next step actions with that information (e.g., withdraw money out from your account). Phishing itself is not a new concept, but it's increasingly used by phishers to steal user information and perform business crime in recent years. Within one to two years, the number of phishing attacks increased dramatically (Leon, 2008).

1.2 PROBLEM OF THE STUDY

In android phone, information has played a major role in our daily life. The act of queuing at the bank for payment of money or receiving of money has become tough and major problem in the bank. Due to the issue of manual process in sending information, internet comes in and changes the view of information system. Information of people can now be provided through the internet, registration and transaction of money could now be sent through the internet

facilities. Phishing problems occur in many different areas in information technology majorly in Email sending and website that disseminated information to users. Phishing occur in email whenever a message is sent to a user of the email that information provided through the bank website by the user is invalid and in order to correct or detect you are the right owner of the information user needs to click on the link provided by the bank for validating in which the email link is not the right link to the bank provided.

Below is the phishing problem in general system:

- i. Stealing of personal information during login credentials through impersonation.
- ii. Attacking the users' email in order to steal important information from the user.
- iii. Attacking the domain name system of the organization in order to impersonate user information to their self-interest.
- iv. Insecurity among information system has complicated the use of phishing in organization.

1.3 AIM AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The aim of this project is design and implementation of a secure anti-phishing system in Android phone which will eradicate the issue emanating in security due to security issue. The objectives of the study are To:

- i. Secure user login credentials through login life span and time schedule.
- ii. Running malware scan in order to kick against phishing problem that occur in an individual's email.
- iii. Secure Domain Name System in order to protect any form of phishing problems that can occur through the bank DNS.
- iv. Setting a security question for the user to answer in order to prove their ownership right of the information requested for.

1.3 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In order to protect the android phone from phishing problems, the focus of this study is limited to the transaction system due to the complexity of this project. The study review how to fish out any forms of phishing problem that may occur in transactional system and how such problem could be totally solve will the use of anti-phishing application.

1.4 LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Hard time is not a new phenomenon to an ordinary Nigerian but to the student researcher, it is even worse. Time and finance posed a lot of constraints to the work. Consequently, difficulties were encountered during the collection of primary data. Most of the administrators, system engineers and clerks visited reluctantly refused interview for one reason or the other and being referred to, the organization from one personnel to the other not excluding even security men. Books related to this topic are relatively scarce and could only be gotten from the internet, which took a lot of time and money. However, with persistence and perseverance reasonable facts were finally obtained.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The proposed system shall be design using a Unified Modelling Language (UML) for the structural and behavioural design architecture. More so, the new system shall be implemented using Java with Android studio IDE and also the information of the new system shall be stored in the database using SQLite database which happen to be serverless database. The proposed system shall be tested using Android Emulator called AVD version 12.

1.6 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

Security has become the problem of nowadays mobile phones especially internet based android phone, for every mobile phone to be highly secured and effective in usage, they must

give room to anti-phishing system. This project gives room to student to learn many things about security and how phishing problem could be solved.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Quoting from Anti-phishing work group, “phishing is a form of online identity theft that employs both social engineering and technical subterfuge to steal consumers’ personal identity data and financial account credentials. Social-engineering schemes use ‘spoofed’ emails to lead consumers to counterfeit web sites designed to trick recipients into divulging financial data such as account usernames and passwords.” (Keasey, 2015).

Phishing has been around since 1995 but became more prominent in July 2003 when phishers began to actively target large financial institutions. Before 2003, phishing was almost unknown. It was generally used only in reference to steal AOL users’ credentials. As time went by, phishing started to be popular in 2004, almost 2 million U.S citizens had their check accounts raided by cyber-criminals. With the average reported loss per incident estimated at \$1200, total losses were close to \$2 billion. U.S. consumers were scammed out of roughly \$3.2 billion over 2007 from phishing scams, a significant increase over last year, according to a survey, produced by Stamford Conn.-based research firm Gartner Inc. (Keasey, 2015).

In recent years, the attack on online banking system has become more and more popular. One reason is that an increasing interest from financial institutes to offer online services. We can find one example in an online service provide company- Alibaba. Most people have never heard of Taobao - an online trade site owned by Alibaba in China. But in recent years, this company has gotten a rapid development. A survey shows that Taobao's market share increased from 9% to 40% in 2004 (Keasey, 2015).

2.2 Phishing

As the definition suggests, phishers use social engineering and several technical tricks to achieve their aim that is spoofing the users. In this section, we will discuss the origins of “phishing” and some phishing-relative organizations.

2.2.1 Origins of the Word "Phishing"

Actually “Phishing” is made by two words, “phreak” and “fishing”. Phreak, a word construct by phone and breaking, was coined by John Draper who is a famous hacker in history. Blue Box is an invention of his. He used Blue Box to hack the telephone system by sending a specific tone to the phone switches, and then the call would be free. Many hackers and hacker organization use ph, from phreak, as their nicknames. Talking about phishing, we know phishing is using a bait to spoof the fish, if it is beguiled by our bait, we will catch it as our prize. Here the email is the bait; the users who receive the emails are the fish. Therefore the two words can clearly explain the essence of stealing the online accounts and is now a well-established term (John Drapper, 2015).

The first reported phishing incident is that phishers stole the American Online (AOL) accounts from unsuspecting AOL users during 1990s. Just one year later, phishing attacks changed their target from the AOL to some financial companies and users for the purpose of stealing money. The users of online financial companies, Paypal, and EBay are the most popular targets for phishers now.

Phishing emails are actually just another form of spam. It is a subset of the category scam. The information stealing goal makes phishing special while spam is just useless information which is more or less harmless to the users. This means phishing are much more targeted and they usually target a bank or an online trading service. Social networking systems are also important targets for phishing. Experiments have historically showed a success rate of over 70% for phishing attacks on social networks.

2.2.2 ISP

An Internet service provider (abbr. ISP, also called Internet access provider or IAP) is a business organization that provides consumers or businesses access to the Internet and related services (Frank, 2010). As the companies are developing, they may provide a combination of services including Internet access, domain name registration and hosting, and web hosting.

There are thousands of ISPs all round the world, no matter big or small, they all provide Internet access service to their clients. If a phisher want to put their phishing website online, they must get this service from an ISP. So once we find a phishing site, the best way to stop the service is to inform the ISP. Furthermore, we can find the registered information of the persons and send them to the court. Today most phishing sites are registered by the 10 largest ISPs in USA (Debtoriae et al., 2016).

These ISPs have their own policies about domain registering. We need to know these policies to have better information about what kind of domains the phishers can use.

2.2.3 Anti-phishing organizations

Many organizations are concentrating on phishing monitoring and research. Below are several famous organizations in the anti-phishing field.

Anti-phishing Work Group: a group where you can report the phishing and get lots of information about phishing. They have an official website for collected phishing events and work together with many group companies (Kotlers, 2010).

CNCERT/CC is a functional organization under Internet Emergency Response Coordination Office of Ministry of Information Industry of China, who is responsible for the coordination of activities among all Computer Emergency Response Teams within China concerning incidents in national public networks. It provides computer network security services and technology support in the handling of security incidents for national public

networks, important national application systems and key organizations, involving detection, prediction, response and prevention. It collects, verifies, accumulates and publishes authoritative information on the Internet security issues. It is also responsible for the exchange of information, coordination of action with International Security Organizations (Edward J, 2011).

IRIS-CERT is Red IRIS' security service, and is aimed to the early detection of security incidents affecting Red IRIS centers, as well as the coordination of incident handling with them. Proactive measures are in constant development, involving timely warning of potential problems, technical advice, training and related services. (Kettik, 2016).

The Messaging Anti-Abuse Working Group (MAAWG) is a global organization focusing on preserving electronic messaging from online exploits and abuse with the goal of enhancing user trust and confidence, while ensuring the deliverability of legitimate messages. Many anti-virus software companies are also taking some efforts in the phishing research. If we find some suspicious incidents, they are also the places where we can report it.

2.3 Spoofing technology

For achieving the aim of beguiling the users, phishers have their ways and technologies to success. The two main mediums for sending the phishing files are email and instant message. The reasons why phishers can succeed are the use of social engineering and the flaws of some internet protocols and tools. In the context of phishing, two spoofing technologies widely used are email and the web (Wettard, 2010).

2.3.1 Email spoofing

Email is the most popular and basic way used for phishing, because it is very easy to send to a large amount of users. People who send spam generally send millions of e-mails at a time. To maintain the high volume of e-mail generation, phishers use bulk-mailing tools. These

tools generate unique e-mail headers and e-mail attributes that can be used to distinguish e-mail generated by different mailing tools. They will also set up a fake Web site to which the user is deceived to visit. The site contains images from the real Web site, or it can even be linked to the real site. On the Web site, the users are required to update their financial or personal information for some emergency reasons. After the users input their information, it will be sent to the phishers by mails (Adams, 2014).

The format of the email can be either text or HTML. Almost all scam emails are HTML based, simply put this means they have colours, pictures and other text formatting. The main advantage to the scammers of HTML emails is that it allows them to hide the real URL of a website behind one that looks genuine. Text emails are much simpler and plainer, and cannot hide URL's. Occasionally an HTML email is made to look like simple text to exploit awareness of this fact (Reo Johnson, 2010).

2.3.2 Web site spoofing

A faked web site is almost identical with the real one. They have the same frame structure, and most of the frame could actually be copied from the legit web site. However a tiny portion of one frame could be changed, the users cannot recognize it even if they have been surfing the related legitimate web site for many times.

There is another attack which does not need to create a fake Web site, the phishers simply involve a redirect script that collect the data and forward the victim back to the real web site. As the protection to the finance web sites are quite strong, this skill is method is not used very common today. But an incident happened before in China, a phisher used a Java Script on the ICCBC which is one of the biggest banks in China, causing many costumers' account to be compromised (Olaofe, 2009).

2.3.3 Instant messaging

As the usage in instant message software such as Window Message, Skype, and Yahoo Message have increased, the number of phishing incidents have also increased in the instant message word. For this new form of phishing, Bakosto wrote "It is important to understand that most instant messaging systems use only weak authentication schemes. Instant messaging is not a tool for exchanging confidential information. Only few instant messaging systems allow for encryption and sophisticated authentication. If you need instant messaging to communicate confidential information, use a system that allows you to control the server and provides for encryption and reasonable authentication. Jabber is an example of a free package with these capabilities." (Bakosto, 2015).

As it is hard to detect an instant message phishing attack, currently there is not an effective way to deal with it. What we can do is tell persons to be more careful about the information relative to their personal details. As one of the most famous instant messaging chatting software, MSN plays an important role for spreading phishing files. The users often receive some files sent by their buddies who they trust in, but they are actually dangerous virus files. Once the users download it, they may be monitored by phishers. We can see an example of a phishing file spreading on MSN in Figure2.4.

Figure 2.2: An example of instant message phishing attack in MSN Live Messenger.

Source: Reskot, 2016.

2.3.4 Phone phishing

Phone phishing was historically used by phishers even though at that time they didn't know it was phishing. However it is still a medium used today. Phishers recreate a legitimate sounding copy of a bank or some finance institutes phone answerer. They will publish the phone number, usually by phishing mail, to the public. Once the victim is calling the number, the copied voice will be used to spoof the user to release information to the phisher (Peter T., 2016).

2.3.5 Harming

Normally we identify the web site on the Internet by their visible domain names, such as "google.com". In the user's computer, there is a stored list of domain names, called hosts files, which link an IP address to a domain. Once the user want to open a webpage, the computer will check the host lists first. If the domain of the webpage exists in the host list, the computer will direct the user to the IP address stored in the list. Else if the webpage does not exist in the host list, the computer will check the DNS server on the Internet to find the corresponding IP address of the webpage. For example, google.com is directed to 66.249.93.147. Though it brings us

much convenience, a big flaw could be used by pharmer. The pharmer can access a user's computer by means of a virus or Trojan horse and change the hosts file inside. Once the user wants to open one special web page, the computer will check host file to get the IP address. The pharmer can now misdirect the client's web request to another faked web server. Another similar way is changing the information at the DNS sever on the Internet. Both attacks could be launch through malicious programs, such as viruses or trojan horses (Peter T., 2016).

2.3.6 SMTP and HTML

Simple Mail Transfer Protocol (SMTP) is used for mail transfer. It was designed in 1982 and at the time it was intended to be used between limited and trusted users. So there were not many concerns about the security problem However by the time these security issues were exposed it was too late as the protocol had gained popularity and it still continues to be one of the most widely protocols (Adewale S., 2010).

Hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP) is used for the transfer of multimedia documents on the internet. The HTTP is not inherently insecurity as SMTP, but it suffers from a lack of standardization and the heterogeneous usage of web browsers such as FireFox, Internet Explorer and Safari. Many attackers can use flaws in the browsers to spoof the users such as www.b1gbank.com which is a phishing site but most persons will see it as www.bigbank.com just because the number "1" is similar with the letter "i".

2.4 Anti phishing

Normally we can find some anti-phishing plug-in systems in browsers or operating system. They can just alarm the users that it is probably a phishing attack, but the user could click the phishing link all the same. With our intended system, we can quickly shut down the site or distribute information used to update anti-phishing software. It is more secure than before.

According to the general idea about how phishing works, it's time to find a way to prevent it. There are many anti phishing products working on the Internet and the users' computers now.

It is often integrated in web browsers and email clients. Internet Explorer (IE) and Firefox are the most common web browsers. Microsoft has a phishing filter in IE7; an access to a phishing sites will be blocked. In Firefox 2 there is a list of known phishing sites. The list is stored both in the software and on the Internet. Again the user will be blocked if he tried to access one of these sites (Nicolas, 2010).

Phishing/pharming filter, built-in anti phishing plug in web browsers, and augmenting passwords login are very popular techniques used in anti-phishing products. Phishing filter will detect the mail to see if it is a phishing attack or not. If it is, the e-mail will be blocked. Augmenting passwords login is used in some banks, such as ICCBC. The client has a unique card that has a series of numbers using when he/she want to login to the account. The server of the bank will send a random secure number to the users and the user will check the identification number by using the secure number and send an acknowledged number back.

Another effective way is education. Phishing attacks are often quite simple and its features are quite obvious. The best way to avoid being phished is to know what phishing is, how it looks like. Example are checking your toolbar to see if the web page is the link you want to open, pay more attention about the mails that requires your personal information and so on.

2.5 E-mail detecting system

In this part, I would like to introduce the whole system first. After giving you a general architecture of the anti-phishing system, I will concentrate on my part that is e-mail detecting system. This specific part of the system will use an e-mail database as an input. After running the e-mail detecting system, it will work out the important and useful information about the phishing e-mails (Ahmed, 2010).

2.6 Architecture of anti-phishing system

In the whole system, we have an e-mail accounts creation system, mail detecting system, phishing mail analyse system, and warning system. In figure 3.1, we can see all the

involved parties in the phishing and anti-phishing activity. They are phishers, anti-phishing systems, ISP, faked website, legitimate web site and target users.

Figure 2.3: Architecture of anti-phishing system (Nicolas, 2010)

Through the figure 2.3 we can set an overview the process of the system. Firstly, the accounts-creating system creates thousands of email accounts that will be harvested. E-mails will include normal ones, spam and phishing ones. We will put these e-mails into a database. The next part is the main part of the system, anti-phishing detecting. We will use features of the phishing e-mails to diagnose whether they are phishing or not. If there are phishing e-mail, we will process further to check the details of the mails including the domain information, the technique that phishers used, and the attacked websites. Then we will alarm the attacked legitimate websites to do some protecting options about the attack and inform the Internet Service Provider of the phishing sites to block the phishing site. We will also inform the anti-virus and firewall

software companies to update their products to protect from this new phishing attack. There are now several ways to stop the phishing attack. First the site will be shut down by ISP. If that fails the phishing e-mail will be filtered of and lastly firewalls will block attempts to access the site.

2.6.1 Process of the system

i. Create a system to create email accounts automatically, and harvest the e-mails

At first, we build a system which can create new email accounts in many common mailbox providers such as Yahoo, Hotmail, etc. Then we will publish the addresses on Internet so that the phishers can find them. We keep these accounts activate and collected the e-mails which will be used in the analysing part of the anti-phishing system. As this part is not very related to anti-phishing theory, it was not developed as part of this thesis.

ii. Classify spam or phishing

After harvesting enough e-mails, it's time for us to create a database for all the e-mails. The e-mails are stored as text files. Then we begin to analyse the mails to detect whether they probably phishing mails or not. Below are the features that could be used to detect the phishing e-mail.

Blacklist of the phishing websites. We collect and update the database of the phishing information on the phishing website like phishing IP address in a blacklist. We will simply search the database to see if they are inside the blacklist when we are scanning the e-mails.

There are some blacklists on the internet we may collaborate with, one is <http://www.spamcop.net/>

White list: We can also collect legitimate websites in a white list. If the e-mail's list to a website exists in the white list, we can conclude that this e-mail is not a phishing e-mail.

Age of domain: Normally the phishing mails will lead the users to a spoofed website. Here the users will be required to fill in their account information. The faked site cannot be active for a long time because the Internet Service Providers will learn about them and shut them down. In

addition, many phishing sites have domains that are registered only a few days before phishing emails are sent out.

We measure age of this site, through table 2.2 we can tell the average online time of the phishing site is 3 days.

The special symbols in UR: In some phishing sites, they use a few special symbols in its URL to spoof the users. For example: `www.legitimatesite @ phishing site.com` or IP-based URL: `HTTP:// 192.168.1.1/paypal`.

Number of dots in UR: Phishing sites often use many sub-urls. The beginning part is similar to the legit site, so the clients may believe it is the legit site indeed. I found that phishing pages tend to use many dots in their URLs but legitimate sites usually do not.

Information in the content of the mail: For most phishing mails, they have the same purpose to acquire sensitive information. So they all have the input or hyperlink to lead the user to send out their information. Also the mail usually is HTML format; we can e.g. scan `<Input>` tags for “Credit card” or “password”. If it contains this information, it probably is a phishing mail. As an example the hyperlink, `paypal.com` will show `paypal.com` in the e-mail (Nicklas Karlsson, 2015).

Output an information list of the phishing mails

When we get to the previous part of the system, most e-mails getting this far will be phishing e-mails. We make some further information from the emails. We have the database which contains information about all the phishing mails. Then we need to collect the information in the mails about domain name, the registered time, the expired time, the registered person or company. I use a program to read the text of the phishing mail and extract the link. Then I access the WHOIS.org, searching the information of the domain. Finally I format the information and output it for further processing in the system.

In figure 3.2 are a number of detected phishing e-mails that I will use as input in my e-mail detecting system.

- eBay_Item_Not_Received_Dispute_Opened_for_Item_#9303607451_1.eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409124.eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409636.eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409636.eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409636_(1).eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409636_(2).eml
- eBay_Unpaid_Item_Reminder_#4604409636_(3).eml
- EbayInc.AnnualUpdateofRecords.eml
- Important_-_Concerns_about_your_account_security.eml
- Important_News.eml
- Internetbackings_sakerhetssystem_fornyelse!.eml
- Message_from_eBay_Member.eml
- NORDEA_BANK-Fornyelser_av_online-bankskyddssystemet.eml
- NORDEA_Officiell_Information.eml
- NORDEA_uppdatera_mjukvaran.eml
- NORDEA_viktig_information.eml
- NORDEA-INTERNET_SECURITY_UPDATE.eml
- Officiell_Information.eml
- Password_Change_Required.eml

Figure 2.4 Phishing mails

After inputting one file, the system will check the content of the e-mail and search for a phishing link. It will then search for information of the domain on the Internet. Rearrange the HTML information and output the required list.

In figure 2.4 we can see the entire process of the system. First I input the name of phishing e-mail, and then the system will read the e-mail to extract the main features, and then connect to Internet to find out the domain information.


```
<terminated> Main [Java Application] C:\Program Files\Java\jre1.6.0_05\bin\javaw.exe (2008-4-22 下午10:14:17)
input the name of the phishing mail:
NORDEA_BANK-Fornyeler_av_online-bankskyddssystemet.eml
*****
Mail Subject:
Subject: NORDEA BANK - F&#246;rnyelser av online-bankskyddssystemet
*****
Received Date:
Day:22
Month:3
Year:2007
*****
Targeted User: <nicke@inbox424.swipnet.se>
Links:[http://202.201.106.11:8081]
*****
expiration and creation date of the domain:
 05 May 2010 00:00:00
 04 May 1995 00:00:00
```

Figure 2.5 Input and output screen

4) Warning system which is used to inform the users, the Internet Service Provider and other companies

In this part of the system, we are planning to implement a function module which can alarm the users that there is a phishing site in the e-mail, inform the companies responsible for the domain registration that there is a probably phishing site exists in its server, tell the attacked legitimate website to do some preventive actions, and request security companies (e.g. anti-virus and firewall companies) to update their products.

In figure 3.4, we can see the companies used by phishers for registering the domain name. Phishers use a ISP to surf Internet and control slave PC to send phishing e-mail. Web hotel is used to set fake web site for anonymous reason, in this part a ISP is also used. Once I find a phishing e-mail, I will inform the responsible ISP to shut down the phishing site.

Figure 2.6 Responsible parties of domain registration

Source: Nicolas, 2011

2.7 The architecture of the e-mail detection system

The e-mail detection system is the main part I worked with. Here we have plausible phishing e-mails as an input. We analyse them in detail, and then extract useful information from these phishing e-mails, such as the domain name, where they are registered, the expire time, which legitimate web sites they are phishing and so on.

Figure 2.7 Three main parts of our system

2.8 Analyzing phishing e-mails

The practical part of the system was developed in Java Version 6 on Microsoft XP operating system. Both development and testing were performed on the same machine.

2.8.1 E-mail Analyze

My program consists of 4 java classes: ReadFile.java, URLTest.java, MothToInt.java, main.java

ReadFile.java. This class is used to read the e-mails database and extract the general information such as the sending data, the domain name of the faked site from the e-mail

The main part of the class is ReadFile (String) function. It requires a String attribute that is the name of the mail. Then it will get out the basic information of the text mail.

In figure 3.6, we can see the parameters and function of the class.

Figure 2.8: The data structure and method in the class

Detect.java: this class is scanning the e-mail to figure out whether it is a phishing mail or not. I use several different features to make this analyzing. They are the numbers of dots in URL, if it requires the user to input some financial information, and the age of the domain. If any function return true, it is phishing mail, otherwise it is considered to be a normal e-mail.

Figure 2.9: Top Used Ports Hosting Phishing Data Collection Servers

We can see from figure 2.5 that HTTP port 80 being the most popular port used at 99.08% of all phishing sites reported. Port 80 is used for browsing webpages, and most information transferring on the internet is using this port.

2.9 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

The definition of E-banking varies amongst researchers partially because electronic banking refers to several types of services through which a bank customer can request information and carryout most retail banking services via computer, television, internet or mobile phones. Burr, (1996) describes E-banking as an electronic connection between the bank and the customer in order to prepare, manage and control financial transactions while Leow, Leon, (2015) states that the term personal computer banking, online banking, internet banking, telephone banking or mobile banking refers to a number of ways in which customers can access their banks without having to be physically present at the bank branch. Therefore E-banking covers all these ways of banking business electronically (Leon, 2015). Electronic banking is the provision of banking services to the customers through Internet Technology (Leon, 2015).

The discovery of Internet and what we called Electronic Commerce has opened various opportunities for online trading all over the world. It has brought the market close to the customers at a relatively low cost. In fact, online purchase reduces cost compared to physical visiting of shops for purchase. Adesina and Ayo, (2010) disclosed that the advent of Internet, electronic commerce, communication technology and how users response to these technology has opened opportunities for many businesses including the financial institution.

Pikkarainen et al., (2004) mentioned two fundamental reasons underlying online banking development and penetration. First, the bank gets significant cost savings in their operations through e-banking services. It has been proven that online banking channel is the cheapest delivery channel for banking products once established. Second, that bank have reduced their branch networks and downsized the number of service staff, which has paved the way to self-service channels. This has been widely appreciated by various customers who felt that branch banking took much of their time and efforts.

On the other hand, customers enjoy self-service, freedom from time and place constraints and reduced stress of queuing in the banking hall. Therefore, time and cost savings as well as freedom from place have been found to be the main reasons underlying online banking acceptance. It was indicated that electronic banking service delivery are the cheapest, most profitable and wealthiest delivery channel for banking products (Pikkarainen et al., 2004). However, not all bank customers engage in the use of e-banking services. There are multiple reasons for this. First, customers need to have an access to the internet in order to utilize some e-banking facilities such as internet and mobile banking facilities. Furthermore, most new online users need to first learn how to use the service. Secondly, non-users often complain that online banking is incomprehensible, difficult to use and has no social dimension which means the lack face-to-face situation at a branch (Karjaluo 2001; Mattila et al., 2003). Third, customers are afraid of security issues (Stephen, 2005).

CHAPTER THREE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 System Architecture

This section focuses on the system architecture of the proposed system in detecting the phishing URLs. The main goal of the proposed system is to detect an URL which is provided as input by the user as a phished, suspicious or legitimate URL. It uses several heuristics in order to determine whether a URL is phished or not. The system design involves designing a User Interface through which user inputs an URL and thereafter, the system displays the output results to the user. Once the input URL is submitted, the system extracts the website features using JAVA standard built-in functions and collect all features which would be used in classification phase for classifying the input URL.

Figure 3.1. - System Architecture of Heuristic Based Phishing Detection System

The following are the steps included in the system architecture shown in Figure.2.

- 1. User Input:** As part of first step, the user inputs a URL (either Phishing or a Legitimate URL) or uploads a file containing URLs. Once the URL is fed to the system, the system extracts features such as number of visitors, number of pages visited by them. These features give a brief overview on category of URL thereby increasing the response time of the system.
- 2. Feature Extraction:** In this step, all the relevant features of the URLs are extracted which are used to differentiate between phishing URLs and legitimate URLs. A URL feature is classified into three groups such as Address-bar based features, Abnormal features, HTML and JavaScript based features and Domain based features. These features will be later discussed in section 3.2.
- 3. URL Classification:** The features which are extracted from the previous step are subjected to different heuristics. A total of 16 heuristics will be used to determine whether a URL is a phished, suspicious or legitimate one. Based on the given heuristics and the features extracted, the proposed rules are applied to these features in order to categorize a URL. These heuristics will be discussed in detail in section 3.3.
- 4. Output the results:** The results are displayed on to the UI in form of tables, graphs which gives a pictorial representation of the results obtained. Also, the severity of the phishing is mentioned for each URL on a scale of 1-5 to determine the impact of phishing on that URL.
- 5. Evaluation:** The results of the classification are evaluated using Precision and Recall. Confusion matrix is generally used to evaluate the classification process by calculating the True Positives, False Positives, False Negatives and True Negatives.

3.2 PROBLEM OF EXISTING SYSTEM

The existing system used in banking sector has a lot of problem and instability which has led to the building of the proposed system that will eliminated the existing problems. Some problems of the existing system are:

- i. Vulnerability issue in the security when login to the organization website using android phone.
- ii. Lack of time schedule after staying logged in without doing anything with the website.
- iii. Email pharming
- iv. Stealing of personal credential of account details through impersonation by phishers.

3.3 ANALYSIS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system has drastically improved the security issue in android operating system, ranging from the login credentials to email attachment or delivery. Phishing has becoming an alarming problem in this recent word of Information Technology due to this problem that has been in existence many researchers have been finding solution to this problem through the process of anti-phishing application. Login in to the system application can be validated through the anti-phishing system.

3.4 MERIT OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed have many advantages to the android phones.

- i. High security standard when login in with your credential.
- ii. Installation of malware into email attachment.
- iii. Time schedule algorithm that will log out user automatically when idle.
- iv. Running security measure when dealing with DNS (Domain Name System).

3.5 SYSTEM DESIGN

3.5.1 Detection of phishing using URL comparison in a search engine

In this research used by Sindhusha Boyapati, the user performs search through a keyword. The application will retrieve keyword, and then URL results from google search API using the keyword, block the URL in search results, display the search results and user then selects a URL from the displayed list which goes through six steps to detect whether a URL is safe or not. This project has two modules such as user module and administrator module. In user module, the user performs a search using keyword. Later, the system returns list of all the URLs related to keyword. The administrator module is used to block a website so that the website cannot be appeared in the search results next time when user inputs the same keyword. The administrator also has a privilege to unblock a site. If the administrator unblocks the site, it appears in the search list whenever user searches for the same keyword. One URL is picked at each time, and this URL goes through 6 tests in order to find whether a URL is phishing URL or not.

3.5.2 Use case diagrams

The use case diagram is used to show the sequence of the actions between the user and the system. These use case diagrams are used to provide a quick summary about the actions of the users who interacts with the system. Use Case diagrams are part of unified modelling language which visualize the design of a software system.

the Use-case diagram for heuristic based phishing detection. The two actors mentioned in the use-case are user and attacker. The user inputs the URL whereas attacker creates a malicious URL. After inputting the URL, user don't interact with the system until the output result is displayed to user. The system extracts the features, apply heuristics to the features, classify a URL and display result back to the user.

Figure-3.2 – Use case diagram for heuristic based phishing detection

Describes use-case diagram which describes the URL based features which have multiple use cases such as Subdomains and multi sub domains, special characters, length of the host URL, and security protocol.

Figure 3.3 - Attacking the phishers Diagram

The use-case diagram for the abnormal based features which have 4 use cases such as RequestURL, Anchor URL, ServerFormHandler.

Figure 3.4: Whole system Use-Case diagram

Use-case diagram for abnormal based features Figure.6 describes the Use Case diagram for the HTML and JavaScript based features which includes four use cases such as redirect URL, onMouseOver, Right Click.

3.7 User Interface Design

The User Interface Design highlights the different UI screens such as Home Screen, Feature Page, Classification Window and Visualization Window.

3.7.1 Home Screen

The Home page as shown in Figure.8. lists different modules on the right corner of the page as shown in the Figure.8. The user enters the URL in the text box provided and clicks on next to see the features pages. If a valid URL is entered in the text box, it navigates to the Features Page else it redirects to the home page saying that no page found.

Figure.8 - Home Page

3.7.2 Features Page

The features page consists of feature groups and features listed under each group. Once the user enters the URL and click next, the features page will be displayed with all the features listed in it. All features are displayed as shown below in Figure.9.

Figure 3.4 Features Page

3.7.3 Classification Page

The Classification Module is used to display the Heuristic, Details and Result in the tabular format. The URL is displayed just above the table as shown below in the figure. A search bar is also displayed which is used to search for a keyword or a term.

The heuristic, details and result for the input URL is displayed as shown in Figure.10.

The screenshot shows a classification page for the URL <https://www.google.com>. The page includes a search bar and a table with the following data:

Heuristic	Details	Result
Age of Domain	Age of the domain is Mon Sep 15 00:00:00 CDT 1997	Legitimate
DNS Record	DNS Record exists for the URL	Legitimate
Google/Alexa Page Rank	Page rank for this url is 1	Legitimate
Website Traffic	This website has enough traffic in the last 6 months : 31.6B	Legitimate

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Previous 1 Next

Figure.3.5 – Classification Page

CHAPTER FOUR

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION AND PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

4.1 SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

The system is designed with several interaction cues on each web page that makes up the phone application (anti-phishing in security). These cues are well-defined such as to make several functionalities that the application exposes to collect, process and output data. Access to these functionalities is made possible by the well-designed user interface which embodies several technologies such as AJAX (Asynchronous JavaScript and XML) to process data. The web page is built in a modular form where these functionalities are built into modules. Some of the modules are as follows:

- i. Detect.xml
- ii. Check_login.xml
- iii. register.xml
- iv. antiphishing_detection.xml

4.2 OUTPUT SPECIFICATION

The system is designed in such a way that it efficiently provides output to the user promptly and in a well-organized manner. The format for the several outputs is make available on the output web pages. Output can be relayed using the following page modules:

- i. Login Module: this describe the login of the system for detecting phishing if there is any within the system modules.
- ii. Register modules: this module illustrate the registration platform for new user.
- iii. Detecting phishing modules: this section gives a clear way of detecting and preventing an attack to the system.

Fig 4.2 shows the basic registration form for new user before login in to the full system. It also allows the customer to save the data if any changes are made.

Fig 4.2: My Account Page

Fig 4.3 shows the page for login in of old or existing users of the application. The pages includes the email address or the user and their respective password to be input for fully access of the application.

Fig 4.3: Login Page

Fig 4.4 below shows the main hoem page of the application. This home page receive an internet connection in order to display for blogging post from the application that will allow user to read and fully participate in it. Unauthorized user or phishers can not be actively perform due to denial in registration.

Fig 4.4: Home Activity

4.3 INPUT SPECIFICATION

The system is designed to accept several input details efficiently through input forms and user clicks. The data captured through the user keystrokes and clicks are received by specific modules on the system and relayed to the back-end of the system for processing. Input is collected using the following page modules:

- i. Index.xml: This is used to capture preliminary user navigation information and preference information which gives the system a method of personalizing the page for the user on the next visit.
- ii. Customer login.xml: This is used to capture information about the administrative personnel who controls content and display on the system.

This allow new user to register and allow returning user to logs in after the homepage he/she is expected to enter the Login Name and Password. When this information entered into the required field the system connects to the database to verify that the information entered is valid, if the information is valid and belongs to a customer then My Account page will be shown, else an error message will be shown.

Fig 4.6 allow existing user or customer that does not remember his/her password and interested in getting it back for login purpose. This can be done by entering the Login name and user's e-mail used during registration into the required field.

Fig 4.6: Side bar Page

4.4 CHOICE OF PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

So many programming languages were put into consideration in the cause of designing this web page. A lot of factors were also considered which includes the online database access, data transmission via networks, online database retrieval, online data capture, multi user network access database security, etc. The database system used to implement the back-end of this system is MySQL. MySQL database is a robust database that can guarantee database integrity,

database protection and accommodate large database. Access to the system was made possible by a graphical interface (phpMyadmin) with an ISAM engine. The phpMyadmin is very user friendly and can be modified programmatically.

4.5 SYSTEM REQUIREMENT

Computer system is made up of units that are put together to work as one in order to achieve a common goal. The requirements for the implementation of the new system are:

- i. The Hardware
- ii. The Software

4.5.1 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT

For the effective implementation of the new system, the following software has to be installed on the computer

- At least Windows Xp, Windows 7 or Vista
- MySQL
- PhpMyadmin
- Android Studio
- Fireworks
- Wampserver

4.5.2 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

- 1GB RAM and above
- 2GB HD
- Printer
- Keyboard
- Intel Pentium
- Mouse

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

Phishing attacks through URLs and Email in android phone is one of the major issues faced by the Internet Community because of the online transactions performed on a day-to-day basis. The phishing attacks cause severe loss to companies, customers and web users. Social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn have been the victims of phishing. However, there are anti-phishing tools available which can help users to detect phishing attacks and prevent them.

The Phishing Detection System detects the malicious URLs and specify the reason for classifying a URL as phishing which will help the users to be aware of such malicious and suspicious URLs. After the user enters a URL, the system provides 16 heuristics for the user to select and apply on input URL to determine whether a URL is malicious or legitimate. It stores all the input URLs in the database which can be retrieved for the later purpose. Apart from this, the system also displays the phishing results in form of pie charts and bar graphs.

The testing is done on all legitimate websites as well as malicious websites which are collected from phish tank. The testing is done on combination of multiple heuristics as well as on individual heuristics to ensure the efficient functionality of system. From a set of URLs tested, majority of the URLs have been classified as correctly by the system. The evaluation of the system is done using a confusion matrix which lists the True Positives, True Negatives, False Positives and False Negatives. Once all this information is collected, the precision and recall are calculated for the system. Based on heuristics selected by the user, the precision and recall varies accordingly. For a better precision and recall, the false

positives and false negatives can be reduced which will improve the accuracy of the classification.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Using anti-phishing application in fishing out malicious user has become an important role in android phone or other important phones. In order to secured personal credentials of an individual in android system, security must be placed in a way that will allow transaction or financial institution to be secured.

I recommend the use of anti-phishing application to detect and secured financial transaction in banking sector purposely Union Bank as a case study. Mere using the application will protect the customer details and private information of an individual. The protection is ranged from login credentials to transaction of payment to inter-banking activities from which no intercessor could hijack the personal information.

To all students who wishes to work on securing banking sector can also proceed from where this study stopped or working on security protection application such as anti-pharming, brute force attack, cryptanalysis and other security measure.

REFERENCES

- Alexander Pons, Hudson, R., & Keasey, K. (2004). *Electronic trading platforms and the cost-effective distribution of open market option (OMO) pension annuities*. International Journal of Information Management, Miami: pp 187-195.
- Biago Bossone and Massimo Cirasino, (2015) "The Oversight of the Payment Systems: A Framework for the Development and Governance of Payment Systems in Emerging Economies" The World Bank, July 2001, p.7
- Biagio Bossone and Massimo Cirasino (2013) Concept of anti-phishing system in modern age using cryptanalysis techniques, Op.Cit, p.7
- De Leon, E. (2008, August 23). Best Online Food Ordering System. Restaurant Checklist.
- John V. Mullane, Ivang, R., et al. (2007). *E-markets in the battle zone between relationship and transaction marketing*. *Electronic Markets, New Jersey: pp 393-404*.
- Kroc, Ray (1977). *Grinding it out: The Making of McDonald's*. Chicago: Contemporary Books.
- Lee C., Yeh Y., Chen D. & Ku K. (2000) A Share Assignment Method to Maximise the Probability of Secret Sharing Reconstruction under the Internet. Payment Systems: Design, Governance and Oversight", edited by Bruce J. Summers, Central Banking Publications Ltd, London, 2012, p.3
- R.G. Javalgi et al. (2008). *Electronic markets and virtual value chains on the information superhighway*. Sloan Management Review, pp 62-72.
- Pikkarainen (2000) frequently Asked Questions about Today's Cryptography. RSA Laboratories
- Stephen Hawk, (2005). *Collaboration in the consumer product goods industry- Analysis of marketplaces*. In 10th European Conference on Information Systems (ECIS). Poland: Gdansk.

What is a Payment System?" (PDF). Federal Reserve Bank of New York. 13 Oc 2000.

Retrieved 23 July 2015. Check date values in: |date= (help)

Treese G. & Stewart L. (1998) Designing Systems for Internet Commerce.

Addison-Wesley, MA. U.S. Department of Commerce (1998)

The Digital Economy, April <http://www.ecommerce.gov/danc1.html>

Author Citations

1. Acharya, Kamal, Attendance Management System Project (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, Online Food Order System (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, University management system project. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, Online banking management system. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, Online job placement system project report. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, Software testing for project report. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, Burger ordering system project report. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>
13. Acharya, Kamal, Teachers Record Management System Project Report (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4833821> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4833821>

14. Acharya, Kamal, *Dairy Management System Project Report (December 20, 2020)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835231> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835231>
15. Acharya, Kamal, *Electrical Shop Management System Project (December 10, 2019)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835238> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835238>
16. Acharya, Kamal, *Online book store management system project report. (February 10, 2020)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835277> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835277>
17. Acharya, Kamal, *Paint shop management system project report. (January 10, 2019)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835441>
18. Acharya, Kamal, *Supermarket billing system project report. (August 10, 2021)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4835474> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4835474>
19. Acharya, Kamal, *Online taxi booking system project report. (March 10, 2022)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837729> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837729>
20. Acharya, Kamal, *Online car servicing system project report. (March 10, 2023)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837832> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837832>
21. Acharya, Kamal, *School management system project report. (July 10, 2021)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4837837> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4837837>
22. Acharya, Kamal, *Furniture Showroom Management System Project Report (March 21, 2021)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839422> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839422>
23. Acharya, Kamal, *Online Vehicle Rental System Project Report (March 21, 2019)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4839429> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4839429>
24. Acharya, Kamal, *Fruit Shop Management System Project Report (August 10, 2023)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841048> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841048>
25. Acharya, Kamal, *Hall Booking Management System Project Report (December 21, 2023)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841055> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841055>
26. Acharya, Kamal, *Lundry Management System Project Report (October 21, 2023)*. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841059> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841059>

27. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT* (September 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841209> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841209>
28. Acharya, Kamal, *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT* (May 25, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4841210> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4841210>
29. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE DATING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842066> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842066>
30. Acharya, Kamal, *ONLINE RESUME BUILDER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842071> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842071>
31. Acharya, Kamal, *TOLL TEX MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT* (August 21, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842082> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842082>
32. Acharya, Kamal, *Chat Application Through Client Server Management System Project Report* (June 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842761> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842761>
33. Acharya, Kamal, *Web Chatting Application Management System Project Report* (April 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4842771> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4842771>
34. Acharya, Kamal, *Automobile management system project report* (May 25, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846917> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846917>
35. Acharya, Kamal, *College bus management system project report* (April 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846920> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846920>
36. Acharya, Kamal, *Courier management system project report* (May 25, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846922> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846922>
37. Acharya, Kamal, *Event management system project report* (April 25, 2021). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4846927> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4846927>
38. Acharya, Kamal, *Library management system project report II* (May 25, 2020). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4848857> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4848857>
39. Kamal Acharya. *Teacher record management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.46787329/v1>

40. Kamal Acharya. *POST OFFICE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.44494375/v1>
41. Kamal Acharya. *Fruit shop management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261514.42227675/v1>
42. Kamal Acharya. *Dairy management system project report*. Authorea. August 02, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172261513.39402347/v1>
43. Kamal Acharya. *DATA COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER NETWORKMANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.37480177/v1>
44. Kamal Acharya. *School management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.34023165/v1>
45. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY OF CINEMA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254873.30191075/v1>
46. Kamal Acharya. *A CASE STUDY ON ONLINE TICKET BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254872.26972790/v1>
47. Kamal Acharya. *Web chatting application project report managementsystem*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.18588592/v1>
48. Kamal Acharya. *RETAIL STORE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172254871.14590154/v1>
49. Kamal Acharya. *SUPERMARKET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.19145062/v1>
50. Kamal Acharya. *SOCIAL MEDIA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252491.11210579/v1>
51. Kamal Acharya. *Online music portal management system project report*. Authorea. August 01, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172252488.89734698/v1>
52. Kamal Acharya. *COLLEGE BUS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245277.70798942/v1>
53. Kamal Acharya. *AUTOMOBILE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 31, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172245276.67982593/v1>
54. Kamal Acharya. *Ludo management system project report*. Authorea. July 31, 2024 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243999.98091616/v1>

55. Kamal Acharya. *Literature online quiz system project report*. Authorea. July 31, 2024
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172243825.53562953/v1>
56. Kamal Acharya. *Avoid waste management system project*. Authorea. July 29, 2024 DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228528.85022205/v1>
57. Kamal Acharya. *CHAT APPLICATION THROUGH CLIENT SERVER MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172228527.74316529/v1>
58. Kamal Acharya. *Parking allotment system project report*. Authorea. July 29, 2024. DOI:
<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172227078.89966943/v1>
59. Kamal Acharya. *HEALTH INSURANCE CLAIM MANAGEMENT SYSTEM*. Authorea. July 26, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172202020.06707762/v1>
60. Kamal Acharya. *ONLINE TRAIN BOOKING SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 22, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172167914.45160406/v1>
61. Kamal Acharya. *COVID MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT*. Authorea. July 16, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172116616.60220024/v1>
62. Kamal Acharya. *Web development system project report*. Authorea. November 12, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173144769.91595244/v1>.
63. Kamal Acharya. *Tourism management system project report*. Authorea. November 12, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173144144.44637261/v1>
64. Kamal Acharya. *Wireless charging in mobile phone management system project report*. Authorea. November 08, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173109197.71419168/v1>
65. Kamal Acharya. *Human Age and Gender Prediction Management system project report*. Authorea. November 07, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173101380.07915161/v1>
66. Kamal Acharya. *Computer graphics management system project report*. Authorea. November 06, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173092081.18568024/v1>
67. .Kamal Acharya. *Advanced hospital management system project report*. Authorea. November 05, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173083558.80262227/v1>
68. Kamal Acharya. *Library management system project report II*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040872.26706796/v1>
69. Kamal Acharya. *Student Information Management System Project Report II*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040871.12765931/v1>

70. Kamal Acharya. *online musical instrumental store management system project report*. Authorea. October 31, 2024. DOI :<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173040863.37700877/v1>
71. Kamal Acharya. *Leave management system project report*. Authorea. October 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173023610.07320124/v1>
72. Kamal Acharya. *Resort Management and Reservation System Project Report*. Authorea. October 29, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173016279.97900083/v1>
73. Kamal Acharya. *How Google Search Works*. Authorea. October 22, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172961967.70431246/v1>
74. Kamal Acharya. *A case study of social media and its perceived effects to student in academic performance*. Authorea. October 21, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172953990.07689253/v1>
75. Kamal Acharya. *Integration of Sensor Network to Internet of Things (IoT) for Application of Smart Home using Open Source Computing*. Authorea. October 17, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172918899.98182290/v1>
76. Kamal Acharya. *Case studies of common csharp project report*. Authorea. October 16, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172910505.57176321/v1>
77. Kamal Acharya. *Computerized enrollment system project report*. Authorea. October 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.172893928.82416786/v1>
78. Kamal Acharya. *Clothes management system project report*. Authorea. November 15, 2024. DOI : <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173169338.85270304/v1>
79. Kamal Acharya. *Company visitor management system projec report*. Authorea. November 15, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173169336.67380865/v1>
80. Kamal Acharya. *Training and placement cell management system*. Authorea. November 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173161607.73300668/v1>
81. Kamal Acharya. *Virtual Mouse using Hand Gestures*. Authorea. November 14, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173161606.61659157/v1>
82. Kamal Acharya. *COMPUTER INSTITUTE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT*. Authorea. March 13, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174189026.67281599/v1>
83. Kamal Acharya. *Online directory management system project*. Authorea. June 11, 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174965566.61058065/v1>